

The impact of work-based versus school-based learning on cognitive and non-cognitive outcomes in vocational secondary education

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Summary

1. This study examines how work-based learning in vocational secondary education affects students' cognitive and non-cognitive outcomes.
2. Using data from Flemish secondary schools, it finds that replacing school-based learning with workplace experiences can lower numeracy and reading scores in both technical and vocational tracks.
3. However, short-term work-based experiences in the purely vocational track can reduce student amotivation, such that students feel more motivated and interested in their learning after practical workplace experiences.
4. Shorter periods of work-based learning are often less harmful and may even generate positive effects in the purely vocational track.
5. The negative effects are generally more pronounced in technical tracks, where a stronger academic focus is essential.
6. The findings highlight the need for careful integration of work-based learning to balance practical skills with core academic achievement.

1. Introduction

Youth unemployment remains a pressing challenge, with rates in OECD countries often exceeding those of the general population. Vocational secondary education is increasingly recognized as a key tool to bridge

the gap between school and the labour market. In this context, work-based learning, involving apprenticeships or internships, is applauded for its ability to better prepare students for employment. However, concerns persist about the impact of substituting school-based learning with work-based

experiences, particularly regarding cognitive and non-cognitive outcomes. While work-based learning has been suggested to lead to higher levels of motivation and engagement, it may lead to a drop in core academic skills like numeracy and reading comprehension. Additionally, it remains uncertain whether these effects differ between purely vocational tracks and technical tracks, which offer a mix of general and vocational education.

This policy brief summarizes recent evidence from Flemish secondary education (Tobback, Verhaest & De Witte, 2025), where work-based learning has been integrated into vocational and technical programs. In particular, it examines how replacing traditional classroom instruction with real-world work experiences shapes cognitive and non-cognitive outcomes and whether this varies across different educational tracks.

2. Data and Methodology

The analysis uses data from the longitudinal LiSO study, which surveyed a cohort of Flemish secondary education students. These data span from grade seven (age 12) to grade twelve (age 18) and include detailed test scores for numeracy and reading, as well as measures of students' motivation, engagement, self-concept, and well-being. Work-based learning is quantified through program-level reports of scheduled work-based learning hours, focusing on the median number of weeks within each program to ensure accuracy and consistency.

In the study, we distinguish between the purely vocational track and the technical track. While the vocational track is heavily focused on preparing students for the labour market, the technical track includes a stronger emphasis on academic subjects and offers a

route to higher education. This distinction allows for a more precise estimation of the differential effects of work-based learning in these contexts.

Statistical models account for student, family, and school-level factors. This robust approach ensures that findings are not confounded by differences in student backgrounds or school environments. Moreover, by comparing students within the same school and field of study but with different exposure to work-based learning, the study isolates the direct impact of replacing school-based learning with work-based learning.

3. Results

Four main findings emerge from the study. First, for students in technical tracks, work-based learning experiences tend to negatively affect both cognitive and non-cognitive outcomes. Specifically, the shift to work-based learning is linked to lower scores in numeracy and reading comprehension, and to reduced levels of autonomous motivation, engagement, and well-being. Effect sizes are moderate, however, these impacts are meaningful in practical terms.

Second, in the purely vocational track, the evidence is more nuanced. While there are some negative effects on cognitive outcomes when work-based learning replaces school-based instruction, the results suggest that shorter work-based experiences (up to six weeks) may not harm, and could even improve, students' reading comprehension. Longer placements, however, tend to have more negative effects.

Third, work-based learning is found to strongly reduce student amotivation in the purely vocational track, suggesting it can help

students feel more positively about their education when implemented in moderation.

Finally, the evidence on how these effects differ by student social background is mixed. While there is some indication that students from more advantaged backgrounds may fare better with work-based learning, the differences are generally not large.

4. Policy recommendations

Our findings suggest several key policy actions to balance the benefits and potential drawbacks of work-based learning in vocational secondary education.

First, policymakers should carefully consider how work-based learning is integrated into the curriculum, particularly in technical tracks. Our evidence shows that replacing too much classroom-based instruction with work-based learning can undermine students' cognitive outcomes, including numeracy and reading skills. Therefore, policy should ensure that workplace learning does not diminish core academic instruction that is crucial for students' future learning and success in higher education.

Second, limiting the duration of work-based learning experiences is important. Shorter periods of work-based learning – up to six weeks in total per program – appear to have limited or even positive effects on students' non-cognitive outcomes in vocational tracks. However, longer placements are more likely to negatively impact student learning. Policies should thus encourage work-based learning experiences of moderate length to maintain a balance between practical skills and core academic knowledge.

Third, policymakers should support the quality of work-based learning environments. This includes working closely with employers to ensure that internships and workplace experiences are educational and aligned with students' learning goals. Schools and policymakers should provide clear guidance and oversight to guarantee that workplace learning complements, rather than replaces, important academic instruction.

Finally, policies must ensure that all students have equitable access to high-quality work-based learning experiences. While our findings do not show large differences in outcomes based on students' backgrounds, it is important to avoid disparities in the opportunities available to different student groups. Special attention is warranted for disadvantaged students to ensure they benefit equally from workplace learning experiences. By implementing these policy actions, education systems can harness the potential of work-based learning to engage and motivate students, while safeguarding core academic outcomes that are essential for lifelong learning and success in the labour market.

What is BRIDGE ?

BRIDGE is an impact-driven project that aims to build resilient individuals through effective educational transition by formulating robust policy recommendations on education and training policies, the efficient use of public resources and the support of equity and inclusion in education and training systems in the EU.

Further Information:

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